

the animal vulnerable to the effects of other pathogens. According to many studies, the most common cause of calf diarrhea is shown as Rotavirus, but it is reported that it is seen at a higher rate, especially in dairy farms and calves suckling from the mother. The second common factor is Cryptosporidium, but it is more common in fattening enterprises than dairy enterprises, and Coronavirus is reported to be the third common cause. It is stated that the factors that cause calf diarrhea can be determined quickly and minimized with effective treatment. In the etiology of diarrhea in calves; Bacterial agents such as E.coli, Salmonella spp., Cl.perfringens, Campylobacter jejuni, Chlamydia spp., Viral agents such as Rotavirus (group A), Coronavirus, Adenovirus, Parvovirus, Astrovirus, Calicivirus, Bovine Viral Diarrhea(BVD), and parasitic agents such as Coccidia, Cryptosporidium, Giardia, Neoscaris vitulorum are present (DR Snodgrass et al., 1986).

Calves with diarrhea are sick at 0-4 weeks of age, especially at 0-2 weeks; It is reported that 80% of them have an infectious cause, 50% of the positive ones have more than one factor, and 31% of them have two factors (Ok et al., 2012). The defense mechanisms of newborn calves against pathogenic factors are not developed. Since there is no antibody transmission from mother to fetus due to the presence of syndesmochorial placenta structure in cattle and the antibodies are too large, calves are born agammaglobulinemic when they are born, and they are not protected against pathogenic factors until they receive a sufficient amount of colostrum (Aldridge et al., 1992; Reber et al., 2006). Immunity generated by the ingestion of colostrum by calves is known as passive immunity. Passive immunity ends with the destruction of maternal antibodies, which lasts for 3-4 weeks (Neto et al., 2004).

E. coli is the most important bacterial cause of diarrhea in calves. The environmental conditions of the calf, the type of the causative agent, and the immune status of the calf play an essential role in the formation of infection. In etiology, mainly septicemic and enterotoxigenic (ETEC) (F4, F5 (= K99), F6, F41 antigens) O8, O9, O78, O45, O117, and O35 serotypes and lesser enterohemorrhagic (O157:H7) and necrotoxicogenic E. coli are effective. Insufficient, poor

quality or no colostrum in the first hours of birth, poor maternal care in the dry period and late separation of them, lack of vitamin A, not paying attention to the cleanliness of the shelters, feeding with milk with mastitis, not paying attention to udder hygiene are the predisposing factors. It is one of the most important diseases of calves worldwide (Radostits et al., 2007).

Neonatal calves are susceptible to E. coli (K99) infection in the first four days after birth, and watery diarrhea may occur when infected (Foster and Smith, 2009).

The outer part of the small intestine, which has a low pH, provides the necessary environment for ETEC invasion. In addition, loss of infected cells, villous atrophy, and damage to the lamina propria are observed in the small intestine. The bacteria reveal the K99⁺ antigen for attachment (Francis, 1989). In a study, 37 E. coli isolated from calves with diarrhea, K99 (18.9%), F41 (18.9%), heat-stable enterotoxin a (STA) (18.9%), Shiga toxin 1 (Stx1;13.5%), Shiga toxin 2 (Stx2;5.4%) and intimin (8.1%) genes have been reported to be detected by multiplex PCR (Ok et al., 2009). Although it is generally seen up to two weeks of age, it is more effective in calves less than five days old, and infected animals are also a source of infection. Morbidity varies between 30-70%, mortality is between 50-60% in the first three days of calves, and this rate decreases to 5-10% in 8-day-old calves. The incubation period is 1-3 days (Radostits et al., 2007).

Enterotoxin production is one of the essential factors that determine pathogenicity in E. coli strains. ETECs produce mainly two types of enterotoxins: thermolabile toxin (LT), which becomes inactive at 600C for 30 minutes, and thermostable toxin (ST), which can withstand 1000C for 15 minutes. Enterotoxin type differs according to animal species. While more LT is synthesized in strains that spread in calves and cattle, ST synthesis varies according to species (DebRoy and Maddox, 2001; Hossain et al., 2007; Rigobelo et al., 2006). Enteropathogenic (EPEC) E. coli is reported to cause diarrhea due to the destruction of microvilli and release of verotoxin after it invades the small and large intestines (Pospischil, 1989). When calves are born in heavily contaminated environmental conditions, virulent pathogens may settle in the distal part of the intestines

and cause disease before normal adult intestinal flora is formed (Fecteau et al., 2009). Although bacteria survive and are ingested in the small intestines, they must interact with the fimbriae on the microvilli of the small intestine through fimbrial antigens, defined as “K antigens”, in order to become biologically active. K-antigens in the capsule of gram (-) bacteria are characterized by the presence of LPS with O antigens on the cell wall, and they do this with their flagella with H antigens (Foster and Smith, 2009; Hunt, 2010).

The presence of uncontrollable inflammation in infected extravascular tissues plays a role in the pathogenesis of sepsis and septic shock (Buttenschoen et al., 2010). Dehydration with electrolyte loss due to *E. coli*, sepsis due to elevated LPS, and related changes are observed in calf diarrhea (Bicknell and Noon, 1993; Roberts et al., 2011).

Septicemia or coli-septicemia in newborn (neonatal) calves progresses rapidly in the first 2-6 days of their lives and often results in death (Fecteau et al., 2009). Diarrhea of newborn calves due to *E. coli* is a disease characterized by diarrhea that is usually mucous, watery, yellow, grayish or green, sometimes bloody, and, if left untreated, progressive dehydration, resulting in increased electrolyte loss and death (Bicknell and Noon, 1993; Figure 2). In the very early stages of the disease, clinical symptoms are not evident and exhibit similar symptoms to other disease symptoms (Fecteau et al., 2009). Hyperdynamic and hypodynamic phase changes are observed depending on the increase in LPS. The absence of the sucking reflex is a mental state picture that mainly occurs between moderate depression and coma, and it is also reported as non-specific clinical findings (Roberts et al., 2011).

In cases of diarrhea, significant fluid-electrolyte losses occur in animals. As a result of diarrhea, a significant amount of Na⁺, K⁺, Cl⁻ and HCO₃⁻ is lost in the feces. While this causes a decrease in blood pH, plasma HCO₃⁻ value, Na and Cl concentrations in calves, it causes an increase in the base deficit and plasma K concentration. In calves with diarrhea, blood volume decreases due to excessive extracellular fluid loss, it affects the urinary excretion of K, and the excretion of H ions decreases due to disruptions in renal functions and acid-base balance. In addition,

metabolic acidosis occurs due to the rapid increase in H⁺ ions in the blood. In calf diarrhea, H⁺ ions, which increase excessively in the plasma, pass into the intracellular fluid, causing K⁺ ions, 98% of which are in the cell, to pass into the extracellular fluid. As a result, hyperkalemia occurs (Özkan, 2017).

Depending on the systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) that occurs with sepsis, one or multiple organ failures and changes in clinical and laboratory findings due to this occur (Nyguen et al., 2006). Diarrhea, mental changes, stagnation, hyperemia of mucous membranes, low blood pressure, increase in heart rate, coldness in extremities, loss of appetite, hypovolemia, decrease in urine output, high fever (sometimes low fever), increase in respiratory rate (Jacobi, 2002; Cunningham and Nadel, 2008; Fecteau et al., 2009), abnormal changes in coagulation, leukocytosis/leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, elevated (sometimes decreased) blood sugar and hyperlactatemia (Nyguen et al., 2006), disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) and multi-organ failure (Zeerleder et al., 2005) symptoms are observed.

Shock consists of 4 different mechanisms that cause clinical manifestations of acute circulatory failure (Weil and Henning, 1979). Decreases in venous recycling (internal or external fluid losses) resulting from decreased circulating volume is the first mechanism. The second is severe arrhythmias (such as ventricular tachycardia or severe AV blocks) or decreased heart contraction (infarction, ischemia, myopathy, myocarditis). The third mechanism is obstruction due to pneumothorax, pulmonary embolism, or cardiac tamponade. Finally, the fourth reason is unstable tissue perfusion due to loss of vascular rhythm (as a result of anaphylaxis, sepsis, or spinal injury) (Vincent and DeBacker, 2013).

Several mechanisms have been proposed for the development of multi-organ failure. These are: tissue or cell hypoxia, stimulation of tissue apoptosis, translocation of microorganisms or their compounds from the gastrointestinal tract, immune system disorders and mitochondrial dysfunction (Osterbur et al. 2014). Presumably, MODS develops due to decreased oxygen availability and use, changes in cellular metabolism, and

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cardiovascular dysfunction leading to tissue hypoxia. Tissue hypoxia occurs due to metabolic acidosis and decreased oxygen ratio (Evans and Smithies, 1999). Pulmonary dysfunction is a picture of persistent hypoxemia due to increased permeability of pulmonary vessels, pulmonary epithelial damage, development of micro-thrombosis, pulmonary edema, and a decrease in surfactant production (Ware and Matthay, 2000). In addition, the development of oliguria and azotemia shapes renal dysfunction. Acute renal failure develops due to deterioration of renal blood flow resulting from microvascular alternation with the development of hypotension (Evans and Smithies, 1999). Gastrointestinal dysfunction primarily presents with ileus, but the loss of the normal barrier function of the gastrointestinal mucosa may also occur. In addition, losses in the mucosal barrier together with bacterial translocation or absorption of endotoxin contribute to the pathogenesis of MODS (Rombeau and Takala, 1997).

Commonly occurring central nervous system dysfunction may be characterized by depression. However, due to severe damage to neurons, septic encephalopathy may also occur (Papadopoulos et al., 2000).

Since there are many serotypes of *E. coli*, the agent's identification is important in selecting the vaccine to protect from the disease. In case of calf diarrhea, the Latex Agglutination Test is frequently used to identify *E. coli* K99⁺ (Cho et al., 2010). PCR testing helps identify complex to isolate viruses, fungi, culture or bacteria that take a long time to grow. In addition to the above-mentioned diagnostic methods, the diagnosis of enteropathogens can also be made with immunochromatographic test kits (Çitil et al., 2004). The aim of this study is to determine the antibiogram results of *E. coli* cases observed in the province of Aksaray within a limited time period.

Material and Method

Twenty internal organ samples (liver, heart, lung, and mesenteric lymph node) were taken from the calf death cases in 20 different dairy cattle farms located in Aksaray city center and its districts and immediately delivered to the laboratory under cold chain conditions.

Cultivation

5% of sheep Blood Agar (Oxoid) and MacConkey Agar (Oxoid) were inoculated and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours from the collected samples. Gram-negative colonies grown on the media were investigated for *E. coli* by applying various biochemical tests (Winn et al., 2006).

Antibacterial Susceptibility Test

The standard disc diffusion method determined the antibiotic susceptibility of isolated strains (CLSI, 2012). Isolates incubated in tryptic soy broth (TSB, Oxoid) at 37°C for 18-24 hours were seeded on Mueller-Hinton Agar (Oxoid), and antibacterial susceptibility test discs were placed 3 cm apart and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. For this purpose, Amoxicillin (25 µg), Enrofloxacin (5 µg), Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (1.5 µg-23.5 µg), Gentamicin (10 µg), Tetracycline (30 µg), Streptomycin (10 µg), Erythromycin (15 µg), Florfenicol (30 µg), Ciprofloxacin (5 µg) and Cefquinome (30 µg) antibiotic discs (Oxoid) were used.

Results

E. coli was isolated from 12 (60%) of a total of 20 internal organ samples. As a result of the antibacterial susceptibility test, 50% of the isolates were Amoxicillin and Erythromycin, 33.3% Tetracycline, 58.3% Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, 66.6% Streptomycin, 75% Florfenicol, Gentamicin and Enrofloxacin, and 83.3% were found to be sensitive to Cefquinome and Ciprofloxacin (Table 1).

Table 1. Antibacterial resistance in all *E. coli* strains isolated from calves.

Antibiotic	S	I	R
Amoxicillin (25 µg)	6	2	4
Enrofloxacin (5 µg)	9	1	2
Trimethoprim- sulfamethoxazole (25 µg)	7	2	3
Gentamicin (10 µg)	9	1	2
Tetracycline (30 µg)	4	4	4
Streptomycin (10 µg)	8	2	2
Erythromycin (15 µg)	6	3	3
Florfenicol (30 µg)	9	2	1
Ciprofloxacin (5 µg)	10	1	1
Cefquinome (30 µg)	10	1	1

S: sensitive; I: moderately sensitive; R: resistant

Discussion

Although the future of dairy farms is multifactorial, it depends on the calves and heifers taking their place on the farm and participating in the yield (Bhat et al., 2012). Worldwide calf loss means productivity and economic loss. Calf diarrhea is a cause of high morbidity and mortality worldwide (Wudu et al., 2008). Diarrhea is due to many factors; it mainly depends on the environment, infectious agents, disease-causing power of the agents, nutrition, immune system, and complex interactions (Waltner-Toews et al., 1986). It has been reported that 75% of calf losses before the weaning period are due to diarrhea (Uhde et al., 2008; Bartels et al., 2010). In recent years, veterinarians and large enterprises are aware that calf losses and diarrhea seriously affect enterprises (Cho and Yoon, 2014). Neonatal diseases are fundamental problems in calf rearing and cause significant economic losses in our country and the world due to calf diarrhea, growth retardation, deaths, and treatment costs (Radoski et al., 2007). 26% of the mortality rates seen in the first month are due to diarrhea, and diarrhea is a significant cause of neonatal mortality. While the mortality rate due to diarrhea in the neonatal period is 7.8% in dairy cattle farms in the United States, this rate is 2.3% in meat-type cattle. In a study conducted in Canada, the mortality rate due to diarrhea in the neonatal period was 11.8% in meat-type cattle (Couture and Major 1989).

Calf diarrhea is usually caused mainly by viruses, bacteria, and protozoa (Smith, 2009). *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium parvum*, Rotavirus, and Coronavirus are stated as the four most important causes of diarrhea in neonatal calves in the world (Reynolds et al., 1986; Fuente et al., 1998). Some researchers state that the most common agents are Coronavirus, Rotavirus (group A), Bovine Viral Diarrhea (BVD), *Salmonella* species, *E. coli* (specifically K99+), *Clostridium* species, and *Cryptosporidium* species (Bhat et al., 2012).

In addition to these factors, *Giardia intestinalis* has become important due to both zoonosis and its increasing prevalence in recent studies, and more research is needed. *Salmonella* strains and *E. coli* K99+ were reported as the most common factors in diarrhea seen in those less than

two months old. In a study conducted in our country, *E. coli* (K99) was detected in the 1st and 4th week following birth (Al and Balıkçı, 2012). In order to detect *E. coli* (K99) with immunochromatographic test kits, 27.45%, 17% (Balıkçı, 2012), 9.4% were detected alone or in mixes.

This study used *E. coli*, 5% sheep blood agar, and MacConkey Agar to detect enteropathogens in calves brought to Aksaray University Veterinary Health Application and Research Center for treatment. Enteropathogens were identified by cultures and isolates incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours in tryptic soy broth (TSB, Oxoid), grown in Mueller-Hinton-Agar (Oxoid), and the sensitivity of the antibiotics to be used in the treatment was tested by inserting antibacterial susceptibility test discs. It was observed that most of the calves with diarrhea were ignored in the treatment protocols due to the antibiogram resistance of the agents in the previous applications by the breeder or the veterinarians. We believe that by detecting the enteropathogen with antibiogram sensitivity, more effective treatment can be carried out and this will add to the country's economy by reducing unnecessary drug use and calf deaths.

Conclusion

Many calves die each year due to *E. coli* agents. It causes severe damage to the country's economy. In addition, the cost of treatment causes severe economic losses. A total of 20 visceral samples were taken from calf death cases in 20 different dairy farms in Aksaray city center and its districts, and *E. coli* was isolated from 12 (60%) of them. It was determined that the calves included in the study were treated either alone or by one or more veterinarians based on the anamnesis we received from the breeders, and satisfactory results could not be obtained. With specific treatment methods prescribed in line with the determined etiological factors, both deaths due to diarrhea in the neonatal period can be reduced.

Furthermore, the formation of resistance to bacterial agents and unnecessary costs can be eliminated by preventing the use of the wrong drugs. With the studies carried out, the frequency of these factors should be determined, the necessary information should be provided, and the economic damage should be minimized by creating control

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programs. At the end of these studies, both veterinarians and farmers should be made conscious and raising healthier calves should be ensured, and more effective results should be aimed by increasing the importance given to these types of studies and by working with more materials on a broader area regarding neonatal calf diarrhea, which has insufficient information in our country.

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